

Bioremediation of Dye Wastewater Utilising Microbes and Plants Utilising Specific Bioreactors for Water Purification Technology

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ABSTRACT

Bioremediation is an emerging technology which can be simultaneously used with other physical and chemical treatment methods for complete management of diverse group of environmental pollutants. It seems as a sustainable approach for the environmental pollution management, and hence, there is a need for more research in this area. Efforts need to be made to generate a synergistic interaction between the environmental impact on fate and behavior of environmental contaminants and assortment and performance of the most suitable bioremediation technique and another relevant technique that can sustain the effective and successful operation and monitoring of a bioremediation process. Many types of dye wastewaters have been cleaned using bioremediation technology by fungal, bacterial, algal utilizations. The fungus cell wall has biosorption capacity to adsorb the dye particles and degrade them. Similar is with bacterial and algal cell walls but comparatively to a lesser extent.

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INTRODUCTION

Industrialization increases use of dyes due to its high demand in paper, cosmetic, textile, leather and food industries. This in turn would increase wastewater generation from dye industrial activities. Various dyes and its structural compounds present in dye industrial wastewater have harmful effects on plants, animals and humans. Synthetic dyes are more resistant than natural dyes to physical and chemical methods for remediation which makes them more difficult to get decolorize. Microbial degradation has been researched and reviewed largely for quicker dye degradation. Genetically engineered microorganisms (GEMs) play important role in achieving complete dye degradation. This paper provides scientific and technical information about dyes & dye intermediates and biodegradation of azo dye. It also compiles information about factors affecting dye(s) biodegradation, role of genetically modified organisms (GMOs) in process of dye(s) degradation and perspectives in this field of research.[1]

The synthesis of dyes and pigments used in textiles and other industries generate the hazardous wastes. A dye is used to impart color to materials of which it becomes an

integral part. The waste generated during the process and operation of the dyes commonly found to contain the inorganic and organic contaminant leading to the hazard to ecosystem and biodiversity causing impact on the environment. The amount of azo dyes concentration present in wastewater varied from lower to higher concentration that lead to color dye effluent causing toxicity to biological ecosystem. The physico-chemical treatment does not remove the color and dye compound concentration. The decolorization of the dye takes place either by adsorption on the microbial biomass or biodegradation by the cells. Bioremediation takes place by anaerobic and/or aerobic process. The anaerobic process converts dye in toxic amino compounds which on further treatment with aerobic reaction convert the intermediate into CO₂ biomass and inorganics. In the present review the decolorization and degradation of azo dyes by fungi, algae, yeast and bacteria have been cited along with the anaerobic to aerobic treatment processes. The factors affecting decolorization and biodegradation of azo dye compounds such as pH, temperature, dye concentration, effects of CO₂ and Nitrogen, agitation, effect of dye structure, electron donor and

enzymes involved in microbial decolorization of azo dyes have been discussed.[2,3]

DISCUSSION

A bioreactor is an indispensable part of any bioprocess irrespective of whether the process degrades pollutants or produces substances such as foods, feeds, chemicals and pharmaceuticals, and tissues and organs for use in biomedicine. The variety of bioprocesses is tremendous and many different designs of bioreactors have been developed to meet the different needs. In all cases, the bioreactor must provide the environmental conditions necessary for the culture. [4,5]. The specific demands are often conflicting and achieving optimal performance requires attaining the proper balance among the different requirements. Success of a bioprocess depends critically on good design and operation of the bioreactor.[6,7]

Membrane bioreactors for wastewater treatment is a combination of a suspended growth biological treatment method, usually activated sludge, with membrane filtration equipment, typically low-pressure microfiltration (MF) or ultra filtration (UF) membranes. The membranes are used to perform the critical solid-liquid separation function. In activated sludge facilities, this is traditionally accomplished using secondary and tertiary clarifiers along with tertiary filtration. The two general types of MBR systems are vacuum (or gravity-driven) and pressure-driven systems. Vacuum or gravity systems are immersed and normally employ hollow fiber or flat sheet membranes installed in either the bioreactors or a subsequent membrane tank. Pressure driven systems are in-pipe cartridge systems located externally to the bioreactor.[8,9]

An "MBR System" is considered to be a complete and integrated membrane unit (sub-systems) with related components necessary to allow the process to function as desired. An MBR system is often comprised of ten or eleven sub-systems and includes fine screening (headworks), the Membrane Zone and, in most cases, some type of post-disinfection process.[10,11]

An MBR, or Membrane Zone, can best be described as the initial step in a biological process where microbes are used to degrade pollutants that are then filtered by a series of submerged membranes (or membrane elements). The individual membranes are housed in units known as modules, cassettes, or racks and a combined series of these modules are referred to as a working membrane unit. Air is introduced through integral diffusers to continually scour membrane surfaces during filtration, facilitate mixing and in some cases, to contribute oxygen to the biological process.[12,13]

The benefits of MBR includes a reduced footprint, usually 30-50% smaller than an equivalent conventional active sludge facility with secondary clarifiers and media tertiary filtration. The process also produces exceptional effluent quality capable of meeting the most stringent water quality requirements, a modular schematic that allows for ease of expansion and configuration flexibility, a robust and reliable operation and reduced downstream disinfection requirements.

AMTA is the only industry organization that focuses specifically on membrane processes including reverse osmosis (RO), nanofiltration (NF), microfiltration (MF), ultrafiltration (UF), electro dialysis reversal desalination (EDR), and membrane bioreactors (MBR). The AMTA website offers a wide range of proprietary Fact Sheets and a complete Digital Library of presentations, posters, and papers on all topics related to membrane treatment, membrane systems, and regulatory and compliance topics.[14]. Thus many types of bioreactors are used to degrade dye particles by introducing microbes in them.

CONCLUSION

Bioreactor is a closed or open system used to allow maximum contact between the microorganisms and contaminates. In order to design a suitable bioreactor for a particular treatment process, extensive research on the biological system (such as growth kinetics, metabolic activity of microbes, and genetic makeup) is required. In the past two decades, different types of bioreactors have been developed. Some of these are based on modifications in conventional technology including stirred-tank bioreactors, airlift bioreactor, fluidized bed bioreactors, wave bioreactors, and many others which are currently being modified with modern technologies including combined or sequential bioreactors and hybrid bioreactors. Combined or sequential bioreactors are designed for the facilitation of combined chemical, physical, and biological processes[15]

MBR is a physcobiological hybrid process. The membrane provides a physical barrier for hygienically safe and clean water with the help of microbial-ecological treatment that can achieve good public acceptance. It is also well recognized by the experts that the clear membrane permeate makes post treatment easy; then, a variety of hybrid systems having the MBR as the core can be considered depending on the specific quality requirements of the reclaimed water. These advantages make MBR a good device in water reclamation and/or advanced wastewater treatment. The continued push toward stricter discharge standards, increased requirement for water reuse, and greater than before urbanization and land limitations fuel the use of MBRs. However, there is room for improvement to utilize the potential of the MBR fully. The challenges will center on energy saving, ease of operation, simplified membrane cleaning and replacement strategies, and peak-flow management. The international adventure on R&D of MBR technologies continues.[16]

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